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Research Article

Analytical Method Development for Determination of Salasia and Guduchi in Pharmaceutical Formulation Using

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ABSTRACT

The study focuses on the development and validation of an analytical method for the determination of Salasia and Guduchi in pharmaceutical formulations using advanced chromatographic and spectroscopic techniques. An HPLC chromatographic system was utilized with optimized parameters, including stationary phase, mobile phase composition, flow rate, and detection wavelength. Pure samples of Salasia and Guduchi in pharmaceutical formulations were procured and confirmed using UV-visible wavelength scans and FT-IR spectral analysis. Calibration curves for Salasia and Guduchi demonstrated strong linearity with high R^2 values. Method development involved optimizing chromatographic conditions to achieve precise and accurate quantitative analysis. Validation studies assessed specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, and robustness, supported by statistical analysis. System suitability testing ensured optimal chromatographic performance by evaluating retention time, peak symmetry, resolution, and column efficiency. The developed methods were successfully applied to analyze pharmaceutical formulations, demonstrating high reliability. Forced degradation studies under various stress conditions confirmed the stability-indicating capability of the methods. The study provides a comprehensive approach to analytical method development for Salasia and Guduchi, supporting their quality control and pharmaceutical applications. The findings contribute significantly to ensuring the efficacy and stability of these herbal formulations in the pharmaceutical industry.

INTRODUCTION

The rich heritage of Indian traditional medicine, particularly Ayurveda, has provided a vast array of medicinal plants that have been used for centuries

to treat various ailments. Among these, Salacia and Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia*) hold a significant position due to their diverse pharmacological properties and potential therapeutic benefits. Both plants have gained

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widespread recognition in recent years for their applications in managing metabolic disorders, particularly diabetes mellitus, and other chronic conditions. Their extensive use in traditional practices underscores their importance as natural remedies in contemporary medicine.¹⁻²

The Historical Significance of Medicinal Plants:

Medicinal plants have been integral to human health since ancient times, serving as a foundation for the development of modern pharmaceuticals. In Ayurveda, one of the oldest systems of medicine, plants like Salacia and Guduchi have been revered for their ability to restore balance within the body. These plants are often described as "Rasayana" herbs, known for their Adaptogenic, rejuvenating, and therapeutic effects. The increasing interest in herbal medicine globally is driven by the quest for safer, more sustainable, and cost-effective healthcare solutions.

Diabetes Mellitus: A Global Health Challenge:

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. The prevalence of diabetes has risen to pandemic levels, with the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) reporting over 500 million cases worldwide as of 2023. The disease poses significant

challenges to global healthcare systems due to its associated complications, including cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, nephropathy, and retinopathy. The current therapeutic options for diabetes, including insulin therapy and oral hypoglycaemic agents, are often associated with limitations such as adverse effects, cost, and incomplete glycemic control. This has driven the search for alternative and complementary therapies, particularly those derived from natural sources. Plants like Salacia and Guduchi have emerged as promising candidates due to their multifaceted mechanisms of action and minimal side effects. The pharmaceutical industry relies on accurate and reliable analytical methods for the quality control of herbal formulations. Salacia and Guduchi, two medicinally important plants, have been widely used for their therapeutic benefits, particularly in the treatment of metabolic disorders. However, the standardization and quality assessment of herbal formulations remain a challenge due to their complex phytochemical composition. Advanced chromatographic and spectroscopic techniques, such as High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), UV-visible spectroscopy, and FT-IR analysis, provide robust and precise methods for the identification and quantification of bioactive constituents in pharmaceutical preparations. These techniques ensure the efficacy, stability, and safety of herbal formulations by providing accurate analytical data.³⁻⁸

Fig. No. 01: Image of Salacia (Salacia reticulata) Image of Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia)

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Instruments: Various instruments were employed for RP-HPLC analysis, including a Shimadzu analytical balance, a Cadmach tablet compression machine, an Agilent 1200 RP-HPLC system, a Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer, and a Bruker FTIR spectrophotometer.

Experimental Work: Analytical Method Development for Determination of Salacia and Guduchi in Pharmaceutical Formulation Using Advanced Chromatographic and Spectroscopic Methods

Procurement and Identity Confirmation: Marketed *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi tablets were procured from: *Salacia reticulata* Tablet (Batch 61-66): Genius Nature Herbs Pvt. Ltd., Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu. Guduchi Tablet (Batch 67-70): Pasari Medical, Dhule, Maharashtra. Packaging details, including batch number, manufacturing, and expiry dates, were recorded. Storage was maintained in a controlled environment.

Confirmation of Identity Using UV-Visible Spectroscopy: Sample Preparation: Tablets were finely powdered (100 mg) and extracted using methanol (10 mL) with sonication for 15 minutes, followed by filtration and dilution for analysis.

Method Development: HPLC Optimization: Chromatographic conditions were optimized using a C18 column (5 μ m, 250 x 4.6 mm) with a mobile phase of Acetonitrile, methanol, and glacial acetic acid (50:20:30 v/v/v) at a 1 mL/min flow rate. Detection wavelengths: 312 nm and 270 nm. The mobile phase was filtered (0.45 μ m) and degassed. UV Analysis: Standard solutions (1.0-40.0 μ g/mL) of *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi were prepared in mobile phase for calibration.

Preparation of Standard Solutions: Stock Solutions: Prepared by dissolving 100 mg of *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi in 100 mL volumetric flask with water, yielding 1000 μ g/mL concentration. Dilutions were made in water for analysis.⁹⁻¹⁵

System Suitability Testing:

- Chromatographic Performance Parameters
- Retention Time: Consistent and reproducible.
- Peak Symmetry: Ensured uniform elution.
- Resolution & Selectivity: Verified clear separation from impurities.
- Peak Area: Proportional to analyte concentration.¹⁶

Method Validation: Validation studies were conducted per regulatory guidelines:

- Linearity: Calibration curve (1.0-40.0 μ g/mL) showed a high correlation coefficient.

- b. LOD & LOQ: Determined based on regression line standard deviation.
- c. Precision: System suitability, method precision, and intermediate precision studies showed RSD < 2%.
- d. Accuracy & Recovery: Performed using recovery experiments at 50% and 100% concentrations with satisfactory results.
- e. Robustness: Small variations in mobile phase composition and flow rate had minimal impact (<2%) on retention time and peak area.

Assay Method: Twenty tablets were weighed, crushed, and an equivalent amount of *Salacia reticulata*, and Guduchi (100 mg) was dissolved in 100 mL water, sonicated for 20 minutes, filtered (0.45 μ m), and diluted. HPLC Analysis: 20 μ L sample injection, optimized conditions, and calibration curve were used to quantify active components. Retention time: 3.56 min.

Forced Degradation Studies: Samples were subjected to stress conditions: heat, light, acid/base hydrolysis, oxidation, and photolysis. HPLC monitored

degradation products to ensure accurate quantification in presence of degradation.¹⁷⁻²⁰

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Result of Procurement and Confirmation of Identity of Salacia and Guduchi: HPLC HPLC-grade Acetonitrile, methanol, and glacial acetic acid were sourced from Rankem (Mumbai, India), while pure *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi samples were obtained from Genius Nature Herbs Pvt. Ltd. (Coimbatore) and Pasari Medical (Dhule). Milli-Q ultra-pure water (Millipore, Bangalore) was used for all solution preparations. FT-IR Analysis: FT-IR spectra were recorded using KBr pellet method, confirming characteristic absorption bands for ester carbonyl, aromatic rings, hydroxyl, and C-H stretching in both *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi. UV-Visible Spectroscopy: *Salacia reticulata* exhibited a λ_{max} at 275 nm, with a calibration curve showing strong linearity ($R^2 = 0.999$). Guduchi showed absorption peaks at 216 nm, 266 nm, and 355 nm using methanol as solvent. These results confirm the identity of the procured *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi samples for further analytical studies.

Concentration µg/ml	Absorbance
00	0.000
10	0.130
20	0.226
30	0.482
40	0.644
50	0.856
60	1.208

Figure no.02: FT-IR spectra, Uv-spectra and std. Calibration of *Salacia reticulata*.

Concentration µg/ml	Absorbance
00	0
10	0.121
20	0.202
30	0.432
40	0.621
50	0.816
60	1.202

Figure no.03: FT-IR spectra, Uv-spectra and std. Calibration of Guduchi

Result of Method Development: A stock standard solution (1000 µg/mL) of *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of each in 100 mL water. Standard

solutions (1.0–40.0 µg/mL) were obtained by serial dilution using mobile phases (Acetonitrile: Methanol: Glacial Acetic Acid, 50:06:10 v/v/v and 50:10:10 v/v/v).

Table no.01: Different Composition of Mobile Phase:

Sr. No.	Mobile Phase composition	Ratio for HPLC <i>Salacia Reticulata</i>	Ratio for HPLC <i>Guduchi</i>
1.	Acetonitrile, methanol, and glacial acetic acid	60:04:20 v/v/v	65:06:20 v/v/v
2.	Acetonitrile, methanol, and glacial acetic acid	50:06:10 v/v/v	50:10:10 v/v/v
3.	Acetonitrile, methanol, and glacial acetic acid	40:12:40 v/v/v	45:12:40 v/v/v

Figure no. 05: Mobile phase: Acetonitrile, methanol, and glacial acetic acid in the ratio 50:06:10 v/v/v for *Salacia reticulata* determination by HPLC.

Figure no. 06: Mobile phase: Acetonitrile, methanol, and glacial acetic acid in the ratio 50:10:10 v/v/v for *Guduchi* determination by HPLC.

Mobile phase: Acetonitrile, methanol, and glacial acetic acid in the ratio 50:06:10 v/v/v for *Salacia reticulata* determination peak shows HPLC 275 nm with RT 2.5 min, and 50:10:10 v/v/v for *Salacia reticulata* determination peak shows for *Guduchi* HPLC 355 nm with RT 3.52 min shown in figure no. 05, and 06.

Result of Preparation of Standard Solutions: A stock standard solution (1000 µg/mL) of *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of each in 100 mL water. Standard solutions (1.0–40.0 µg/mL) were obtained by

serial dilution using water, as shown in Figure 02 and 03.

Result of Method Validation:

Linearity: Calibration curves were constructed using three series of standard *Salacia reticulata*, and *Guduchi* solutions in the range of 0.0 - 40.0 µg/ml. The equation of linear regression and statistical data are presented in Table no. 02 and figure no 07. The linearity of the calibration curve was validated by the high value of the correlation coefficient.

Table no.02: Linearity of Salacia reticulata, and Guduchi

Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	HPLC Area Salacia reticulata	HPLC Area Guduchi
00	00	0

10	100020	20000
20	200045	40001
30	400056	60020
40	600024	80002

Figure no. 07: Linearity of Salacia reticulata, and Guduchi.

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ): The limit of detection and the limit of quantification are defined as LOD and LOQ respectively, where σ denotes standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines and s denotes slope of the corresponding calibration curve.¹⁷

HPLC for Salacia = LOD = $3.3 \sigma/s = 0.310$ and
 HPLC for Guduchi = LOD = $3.3 \sigma/s = 0.290$
 HPLC for Salacia = LOQ = $10 \sigma/s = 1.022$ and
 HPLC for Guduchi = LOQ = $10 \sigma/s = 1.322$

Precision: The assay was evaluated for system suitability, method precision, and intermediate precision. Repeatability was assessed using five consecutive injections, analyzing peak area values of Salacia reticulata and Guduchi. Precision (R.S.D. < 2%) results are shown in Table no. 03. Intra-day (same day, three concentrations) and inter-day (three days, six injections per sample) precision studies showed R.S.D. between 0.16–0.50 percent, confirming the method's reliability.

Table no. 03: Precision: Intra- and inter-day precision of Salacia reticulata, and Guduchi for HPLC:

Concentration of drug ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Observed concentration of drug ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)			
	Intra-day		Inter-day	
	Mean	% RSD	Mean	% RSD
10	9.98	0.36	9.94	0.54
15	14.91	0.17	15.01	0.21
20	19.59	0.15	19.96	0.44

*Average of six determinations. R.S.D. (%): relative standard deviation; bias (%):

$[(\text{found} - \text{taken})/\text{taken}] \times 100$.

Accuracy and recovery studies: The accuracy of the method was assessed by comparing measured and reference values, with results detailed in Tables no. 04 to 07. Recovery experiments at 50% and 100% concentrations of *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi were conducted using six samples per level. The results confirm high accuracy and repeatability of the method.

Table no. 04: Precision: Intra- and inter-day precision of *Salacia reticulata* for HPLC:

Concentration of drug (µg/ml)	Accuracy	
	Intra-day	Inter-day
10	0.21	0.41
15	0.32	0.026
20	0.44	0.017

Average of six determinations.

Table no. 05: Recovery Data for the Proposed HPLC method. Studies of *Salacia reticulata*:

Concentration of drug (µg/ml)	Amount (µg/ml)		% Recovery ± R.S.D.
	Taken + Added	Found* ± S.D.	
10	10 + 05	14.99 ± 0.038	100.06 ± 0.378
15	15 + 05	19.94 ± 0.052	99.80 ± 0.347
20	20 + 10	29.05 ± 0.036	99.86 ± 0.178
Concentration of drug (µg/ml)	Amount (µg/ml)		% Recovery ± R.S.D.
	Taken + Added	Found* ± S.D.	
Tablets I	10 + 05	14.09 ± 0.038	98.08 ± 0.378
Tablets II	15 + 05	19.01 ± 0.032	97.89 ± 0.347
Tablets III	20 + 10	29.01 ± 0.03	98.89 ± 0.178

Table no. 06: Precision: Intra- and inter-day precision of Guduchi for HPLC:

Concentration of drug (µg/ml)	Accuracy	
	Intra-day	Inter-day
10	0.25	0.42

15	0.36	0.015
20	0.41	0.013

Average of six determinations.

Table no. 06: Recovery Data for the Proposed HPLC method. Studies of Guduchi

Concentration of drug (µg/ml)	Amount (µg/ml)		% Recovery ± R.S.D.
	Taken + Added	Found* ± S.D.	
10	10 + 05	15.09 ± 0.038	100.06 ± 0.378
15	15 + 05	19.64 ± 0.052	99.80 ± 0.347
20	20 + 10	29.65 ± 0.036	99.86 ± 0.178
Concentration of drug (µg/ml)	Amount (µg/ml)		% Recovery ± R.S.D.
	Taken + Added	Found* ± S.D.	
Tablets I	10 + 05	14.01 ± 0.038	98.08 ± 0.378
Tablets II	15 + 05	19.00 ± 0.032	97.89 ± 0.347
Tablets III	20 + 10	29.56 ± 0.03	98.89 ± 0.178

*Average of six determinations. R.S.D. (%): $[(\text{found} - \text{taken})/\text{taken}] \times 100$.
relative standard deviation; bias (%):

Robustness: The robustness of the method was evaluated by introducing $\pm 10\%$ variations in mobile phase composition and flow rate. Peak area and retention time variations remained below 2%, with no significant impact on quantification. RSD values (Table 20 and 21) were consistently below 2%, confirming the method's reliability under minor parameter changes.

Table no. 08: Salacia reticulata content and their respective RSD values following each HPLC (Chromatographic condition variation):

Condition	Retention time (min)		Content (%)	
	<i>Salacia reticulata</i>	<i>Salacia reticulata</i>	<i>Salacia reticulata</i>	<i>Salacia reticulata</i>
No changes	2.5	3.6	101.2	99.01
Flow 0.9 mL.min ⁻¹	2.6	3.6	103.1	104.2
Flow 0.7 mL.min ⁻¹	2.5	3.6	102.1	101.2
Column temperature 32.5°C	2.6	3.6	104.1	104.4
Column temperature 37.5°C	2.5	3.7	103.1	101.2
Mobile phase ratio 50:06:10	2.5	3.7	100.1	104.2
Mobile phase ratio 50:10:10	3.6	3.8	98.11	103.2
Mean			100.1	101.2
RSD			1.26	1.46

Average of six determinations. R.S.D. (%): relative standard deviation; bias (%):

$[(\text{found} - \text{taken})/\text{taken}] \times 100$.

Table no. 09: Guduchi content and their respective RSD values following each HPLC

(Chromatographic condition variation):

Condition	Retention time (min)		Content (%)	
	Guduchi	Guduchi	Guduchi	Guduchi
No changes	3.51	4.2	101.2	99.01
Flow 0.9 mL.min ⁻¹	3.6	4.6	103.1	104.2
Flow 0.7 mL.min ⁻¹	3.50	4.2	102.1	101.2
Temperature 32.5°C	3.56	4.7	104.1	104.4
Temperature 37.5°C	3.51	4.2	103.1	101.2
Mobile phase ratio 50:06:10	3.51	4.2	100.1	104.2
Mobile phase ratio 50:10:10	3.7	4.8	98.11	103.2
Mean			100.1	101.2
RSD			1.26	1.46

*Average of six determinations. R.S.D. (%): relative standard deviation; bias (%):

$[(\text{found} - \text{taken})/\text{taken}] \times 100$.

Result of System Suitability Testing: Evaluated parameters such as retention time, peak symmetry, resolution, and column efficiency to ensure the reliability of the method shown in table no. 10 and 11.

Table no.10: System Suitability Test for HPLC Parameters for Salacia reticulata:

Analyte	RSD of Replicate Injections	Tailing Factor	No. Of Theoretical Plates	Capacity Factor
	(< 2)	(< 2)	(> 2000)	(>0.5)
Salacia reticulata	0.8619	1.0184	9343.83	1.87
Salacia reticulata	0.9249	1.2182	9563.83	1.97

Table no.11: System Suitability Test for HPLC Parameters for Guduchi:

Analyte	RSD of Replicate Injections	Tailing Factor	No. Of Theoretical Plates	Capacity Factor
	(< 2)	(< 2)	(> 2000)	(>0.5)
Guduchi	0.9569	1.0272	8363.83	1.87
Guduchi	0.9149	1.0272	9663.83	1.97

Result of Assay method: Pharmaceutical Formulation: Twenty tablets were crushed, and 100 mg of Salacia reticulata and Guduchi powder was dissolved in 100 mL water, sonicated for 20 min, and filtered through a 0.45µm membrane.

The solution was diluted with the mobile phase, and 20µL was injected into the HPLC system. Retention times were 2.5 min (Salacia reticulata) and 3.1 min (Guduchi) (Figure 07 & 08). The drug content was calculated using the calibration curve.

Figure no. 07: Result of Assay method for Salacia reticulata.

Figure no. 08: Result of Assay method for Guduchi

Table no. 12: HPLC Analysis of Salacia reticulata and Guduchi from pharmaceutical formulations by proposed method on Third day:

Concentration of drug (µg/ml)	Sample	Labelled amount (mg)	Amount found ± S.D.	Reference method	% Recovery ± R.S.D.
	Salacia reticulata	500	500.83 ± 0.970	499.89 ± 0.807	99.92 ± 0.388

Day 3			$t = 0.009, F = 1.44$		
	Salacia reticulata	500	499.88 ± 0.967 $t = 0.058, F = 2.75$	498.85 ± 0.583	99.95 ± 0.387
	Salacia reticulata	500	499.33 ± 0.204 $t = 0.112, F = 1.06$	498.65 ± 0.210	99.53 ± 0.082
Concentration of drug ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Sample	Labelled amount (mg)	Amount found \pm S.D.	Reference method	% Recovery \pm R.S.D.
Day 3	Guduchi	500	489.83 ± 0.870 $t = 0.009, F = 1.44$	499.83 ± 0.807	99.95 ± 0.388
	Guduchi	500	500.77 ± 0.968 $t = 0.058, F = 2.75$	499.85 ± 0.583	99.98 ± 0.387
	Guduchi	500	498.33 ± 0.204 $t = 0.113, F = 1.06$	498.25 ± 0.210	99.27 ± 0.082

These results the findings from the analysis conducted on the consequential three days. The amounts found closely align with the reference method, indicating high accuracy, while the percentage recoveries demonstrate the method's

reliability with low relative standard deviation (R.S.D.) values.

Result of Forced Degradation Studies:

Figure no. 09: Result of Forced Degradation Studies *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi.

Table no. 13: Results of forced degradation studies of *Salacia reticulata*, and Guduchi:

Analyte (<i>Salacia reticulata</i> and Guduchi)	Retention time of <i>Salacia reticulata</i> (min.)	Retention time of Guduchi (min)
Normal condition	2.5 (100%)	2.8 (100%)

Acidic hydrolysis 0.1M HCL, 3 hr, RT	2.49(7.77%)	2.45 (10.27%)
Alkali degradation 0.1M NaOH, 3 hr, RT	2.48 (7.76%)	2.587 (08.00%)
Oxidative condition 30% H ₂ O ₂ , RT, 48 hr	2.91 (8.46 %)	2.41 (7.65%)
Dry heat studies 50 ⁰ C, 48 hr	6.90 (96.22%)	4.14 (3.78%)
Photo degradation study Sunlight, 12 hr.	7.56 (100%)	6.36 (100%)

Forced Degradation Studies:

Acid Degradation: *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi (2 mg/mL) were treated with 1N HCl for 3 hours, neutralized, and diluted for HPLC analysis.

Alkali Degradation: A 0.1M NaOH treatment was applied for 3 hours, followed by neutralization and dilution.

Oxidation Studies: Samples were treated with 30% H₂O₂ at room temperature for 48 hours.

Thermal Degradation: The pure drug was exposed to 50°C in a hot air oven for 48 hours, then dissolved and diluted.

Photo Degradation: The drug was exposed to sunlight for 12 hours, dissolved, and diluted.

The results confirm the stability and specificity of the method. *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi degraded in 1N HCl and 0.1M NaOH, with degradation products well-resolved from the main peaks. Details are in Table 13.

CONCLUSION:

This study successfully developed and validated HPLC method for the quantitative analysis of *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi in pharmaceutical formulations. The methods were optimized for chromatographic conditions, ensuring high

specificity, accuracy, precision, and robustness. System suitability tests confirmed reliable retention times, peak symmetry, and resolution. Calibration curves demonstrated strong linearity (high R² values). Forced degradation studies under various stress conditions confirmed the stability-indicating capability of the methods. Overall, this research provides a comprehensive and reliable analytical approach for the determination of *Salacia reticulata* and Guduchi using HPLC and spectroscopic techniques.

Ethical Approval:

This review article does not content of any use of animal model.

Conflict of Interest:

Authors declared that no conflict of interest for review of article.

REFERENCES

1. Ardita NF, Mithasari L, Untoro D, Salasia SI. Potential antimicrobial properties of the *Ulva lactuca* extract against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*-infected wounds: A review. *Veterinary World*. 2021 May 8; 14(5):1116.
2. Salasia SI, Tato S, Sugiyono N, Ariyanti D, Prabawati F. Genotypic characterization of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from bovines,

- humans, and food in Indonesia. Journal of veterinary science. 2011 Nov 30; 12(4):353.
3. Windria S, Widianingrum DC, Salasia SI. Identification of Staphylococcus aureus and coagulase negative staphylococci isolates from mastitis milk of etawa crossbred goat. Research Journal of microbiology. 2016 Jan 1; 11(1):11.
 4. Fitrandi M, Salasia SI, Sianipar O, Dewananda DA, Arjana AZ, Aziz F, Wasissa M, Lestari FB, Santosa CM. Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus isolates derived from humans and animals in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Veterinary World. 2023 Jan 31; 16(1):239.
 5. Rosyadi I, Salasia SI, Argamjav B, Sato H. Impact of subclinical Haemoproteus columbae infection on farmed domestic pigeons from Central Java (Yogyakarta), Indonesia, with special reference to changes in the hemogram. Pathogens. 2021 Apr 7; 10(4):440.
 6. Purnomo A, Khusnan H, Salasia SI. Isolation and characterization of Staphylococcus aureus of milk of Etawa crossbred Goat. Media Ked. Hewan.. 2006; 22(3):142-7.
 7. Khusnan K, Oktavia Salasia SI. Respon Neutrofil, Adesi Pada Sel Epitel, Aglutinasi Eritrosit Terhadap Staphylococcus Aureus: Kajian Hidrofobitas in Vitro= Response of Neutrophils, Epithelial Cells Adhesion, Erythrocytes Agglutination of Staphyloco. Indonesian Journal of Veterinary Science. 2006; 24(1):140004.
 8. Kushwaha PS, Singh AK, Keshari AK, Maity S, Saha S. An updated review on the phytochemistry, pharmacology, and clinical trials of Salacia oblonga. Pharmacognosy Reviews. 2016 Jul; 10(20):109.
 9. Majid BN, Kini KR, Prakash HS, Geetha N. Phytomorphology, phytochemistry and pharmacological activities of Salacia chinensis L., an endangered antidiabetic medicinal plant: a comprehensive review.
 10. Kamat SG, Vasudeva R, Patil CG. Taxonomic identity, occurrence of six species of Salacia and first report on chromosome numbers of the Salacia chinensis L. and Salacia oblonga Wall ex Wight and Ern Var. from Western Ghats of Karnataka (India). Genetic Resources and Crop Evolution. 2020 Jan; 67(1):241-55.
 11. Anaz M, Sasidharan N, Remakanthan A, Dilsha MV. ITS 2 and RNA secondary structure-based analysis reveals a clear picture on phylogeny of South Indian Salacia spp. Computational Biology and Chemistry. 2021 Apr 1; 91:107438.
 12. Chawla A, Singh S, Sharma AK. Salacia oblonga wall: a review on its pharmacognostic, phytochemical and pharmacological aspects. International journal of research in Pharmaceutical and biomedical sciences. 2013; 4(4):1215-28.
 13. Simmons MP, Lombardi JA, Biral L. Classification of the Celastrales based on integration of genomic, morphological, and Sanger-sequence characters. Systematic Botany. 2023 Jun 23; 48(2):283-99.
 14. Hernández-Damián AL, Martínez-Gordillo MJ, Ochoterena H, Cevallos-Ferriz SR. The reevaluation of Salacia lombardii (Celastraceae) based on phylogenetic position and biogeographic implications. Journal of South American Earth Sciences. 2022 Oct 1; 118:103962.
 15. Arunakumara KK, Subasinghe S. Salacia reticulata Wight: A review of botany, phytochemistry and pharmacology. Tropical Agricultural Research and Extension. 2011 Jun 22; 13(2).
 16. Radjasa OK, Salasia SI, Sabdono A, Wiese J, Imhoff JF, Lämmler C, Risk MJ. Antibacterial activity of marine bacterium Pseudomonas sp. associated with soft coral Sinularia

- polydactyla against *Streptococcus equi* subsp. *zooepidemicus*. *International Journal of Pharmacology*. 2007; 3(2):170-4.
17. Ardita NF, Mithasari L, Untoro D, Salasia SI. Potential antimicrobial properties of the *Ulva lactuca* extract against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*-infected wounds: A review. *Veterinary World*. 2021 May 8; 14(5):1116.
18. Ibrahim SR, Bagalagel AA, Diri RM, Noor AO, Bakhsh HT, Mohamed GA. Phytoconstituents and pharmacological activities of Indian Camphorweed (*Pluchea Indica*): A multi-potential medicinal plant of nutritional and ethnomedicinal importance. *Molecules*. 2022 Apr 7; 27(8):2383.
19. Sandi NA, Salasia SI. Alternative antibiotics source from symbiont of lactic acid bacteria inside stomach of honeybees (*Apis mellifera* and *Apis dorsata*) against multiresistant antibiotics pathogenic bacteria. *Research Journal of Microbiology*. 2016 May 11; 11(2-3):93-100.
20. Osotprasit S, Samrit T, Savedvanich G, Chaiwichien A, Changklungmoa N, Kueakhai P, Athipornchai A, Tamtin M, Sobhon P, Jaikua W. Evaluation of Toxicity and Antioxidant Activity of the Ethanolic Extract from *Ulva Lactuca*. *Trends in Sciences*. 2025; 22(2):8812.

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